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The Role of Corporate Governance in Reducing the Tax Gap

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Abstract

In this study the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms in reducing the gap between corporate taxes and definite expression is evaluated. The assessment by examining the relationship between the percentage ownership of institutional shareholders, the percentage of non-duty members of the Board and CEO of the combined roles (CEO duality tasks) as corporate governance mechanisms and corporate financing gap and definite expression has been made. Research methods, descriptive - correlation between the theoretical and procedure library and its data exchange and reporting of the Company has been obtained. Data sample of 130 companies listed in Tehran Stock Exchange during the years 1385 to 1391 have been selected. Hypothesis, using correlation and multiple regression equations from panel data approach has been tested. The results indicate that the percentage of non-duty members of the board composition, the percentage ownership of the combined roles of CEO and shareholders have no influence on reducing the tax gap.

Keywords: *Corporate Governance, Tax expression and certainty, Percentage of institutional ownership, Non-duty members of the Board of Directors, Combining the CEO*

1- Introduction

The separation of ownership and management, managers as agents of shareholders, the company's manage [15]. Relationship formation, agency, conflicts of interest between managers and shareholders and other stakeholders (including government) is created and there is potentially possible that managers take action in their own interests and not necessarily in the interests of shareholders and other stakeholders, which is said to represent the problem [8]. In this regard, the government as a stakeholder companies to recognize the tax and submit income tax returns by taxpayers are adjustable, does lean. In the meantime, companies, especially listed companies in Tehran Stock Exchange have taxable income and consequently tax calculated in accordance with tax regulations and the State Tax Organization must submit their tax returns. Tax officers must also be submitted affidavits tax payers in accordance with the laws and regulations that deal, the tax should reflect the assessment of the taxpayer's request, pursuant to the provisions of Article 237 of the Direct Tax Code (BC. M.. M.), Foundations of Legal Documents to declare taxes. In such circumstances, if the theoretical principles of corporate governance that recognizes the rights of all stakeholders, in co-exist (which are common to companies with strong corporate governance), the expected tax and the tax expression, which, expressing be identified and the tax laws and regulations; however, a number of factors, including, contrary to some of the direct tax law and accounting standards adopted by the particular cause

discrepancies between accounting profit based on the cost of acceptable accounting standards and tax regulations is based on taxable profit, Not a secret and almost in most countries, even in developed countries are more or less common [4]. But what this study has been given to it, ensure it is claimed to be robust in the face of corporate governance, the rights of all stakeholders to consider, in this issue the expectation of the corporate governance is tax. Therefore the main research question is posed as follows: Is there a relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and expression and certain tax gap? Thus, corporate governance is a mechanism through which it acts, agency problems have been solved [16] and improved quality of information provided by the Company, the rights of shareholders and all stakeholders, including government and public attention takes place [4].

2- Importance and necessity of research

Today, the term corporate governance is a concept addressed and developed in the world of business. Corporate governance is the foundation for relations with interest groups. The main difference in attitudes is to relationships with a range of stakeholders concerned. Corporate Governance at the micro level, the achievement of corporate goals and at the macro level, the community resource allocation plans (Rezaie, 1390). Now with regard to sanctions, including revenues from oil and gas sales revenue has fallen sharply, so in such circumstances there is a need to increase tax revenues. Given that tax corporate tax expression was confirmed in some cases differ in this respect in order to achieve social justice in taxation, must be given up in the shadow of corporate governance mechanisms, transparency, justice (Sportsmanship) , and the rights of stakeholders (including government), the tax gap is the best form of expression and disruption minimized to collect the tax and tricks. So it seems investigate the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms to reduce the tax gap and definite expression in Iran is essential.

3- Literature

Babajani and Abdi (1389) in their study of the relationship between corporate governance and the tax assessed .two companies with good corporate governance have been weak. The results indicate no significant difference between the mean percentage difference between taxable income and definite expression in companies that do not have corporate governance standards, respectively. This is while both companies, the percentage difference between taxable income and definite expression was significant [4]. Shams Zadeh and Zokouri (1387) in a study to identify the causes of the difference between taxable income and tax definitive expression of legal entities engaged. The results indicate that test the hypothesis that there are differences between the tax and definite expression, and the main reason of failing state agencies, non-compliance with legal regulations and make a significant difference cannot be written in a reasonably offices, although there are minor differences is the result of unacceptable costs in excess of the limit prescribed in the tax law [6]. Babajani and Moradmand (1385) expression for the difference between taxable income by the taxpayer and specified by CPAs and both of them realized profit tax set by the tax of the country, the companies that the implementation of Article 272 BC. M. M. Adopted 27.11.1380, the expertise of CPAs use to determine your taxable income have been investigated. The results of this study indicate that corporate governance has no influence on the reasons outlined in that study [3]. Chen et al (2010) in their study found that family ownership could affect the Company's tax policy. They concluded that family-owned companies, family owned businesses that are less boldly about the tax policies they adopt. These results indicate that family owners tend to avoid company stock devaluation of worrying about the risks arising from the activities of a minority shareholder's tax derives from the tax administration to avoid [12]. Mutairi (2010) in a study on corporate governance characteristics impact assessments were searched. They show that the bonus plan as an incentive for managers to invest in long term projects and straw acts as a tax. The findings indicate that financial management, financial management positively benefits the owners and shareholders is associated with higher earnings yield [18]. Sarturi (2008) showed that cross-reactions between Corporate Governance and the Financial was, in fact, on the one hand, the

structural effects of corporate governance rules and corporate tax obligations to meet the other hand, the tax designs (perspective government) and linking them to fiscal strategies (company perspective) can have an influence on the creation of a dynamic corporate governance [20]. Ahmadpour et al (1388) in their study, the effect of non-bound managers and institutional investors in the earnings management behavior were investigated. Test results indicate that the incentive to manipulate these high-profit, non-responsible managers and major institutional investors, are poor role in reducing abnormal accruals anomaly [10]. Desai, Dyke and Zingales (2007) in their study concluded that high tax rates, worsening corporate governance systems and, conversely, low tax rates, improving corporate governance systems, increase tax revenues in will follow [19]. Koh (2003) the relationship between institutional ownership and earnings management in Australian companies reviewed. The results showed that the relationship between institutional investors and earnings management in the form of non-linear and concave, the first increase in the percentage of institutional ownership, management, earnings increased to reaches its maximum, and the peak relationship between variable is reversed. The present study showed that institutional investors have a direct and inverse relationship with earnings management [17]. Norman et al (2005) in their study stated that lower leverage is associated with higher earnings management, the result of many other studies before (including Mizhoski and Hagerman (1981), Skinner (1993) has also been proven [10]. Chang et al (2002) also examine the relationship between institutional ownership and management of income paid and received major institutional shareholders, management and the use of discretionary accruals increase income and hold. Opposite is true when the manager has less incentive to show a profit, major institutional investors, he opened the hold. The results showed that if the manager does not have a profit incentive to increase or decrease, institutional investors have a relationship with earnings management [13]. Hasas Yeganeh and colleagues (1388) in their study on "the relationship between the quality of Corporate Governance practices of listed companies in Tehran Stock Exchange" The sample consisted of 130 participants using multiple regression, concluded that a significant relationship exists does the quality of corporate Governance and corporate performance [5].

4- Research Objectives

This research is trying to gather information and evidence necessary to test hypotheses and analyze research findings and evidence reasonably required for the effect of non-members in the board composition, the percentage ownership of the shareholders and the combination of managing as the criteria for Corporate Governance expression on financial transparency. In other words, the findings of this study is to provide a broad background to provide to the tax affairs of the tax auditors in the accurate diagnosis of help people.

5- Research hypotheses

There is a significant relationship between the percentage ownership of institutional shareholders and the percentage difference between the corporate tax and definite expression.

There is a significant relationship between the percentage of non-responsible managers and the board of expression and certain corporate tax differences.

There is a significant relationship between the CEO and the percentage difference between the combined corporate tax and definite expression.

6- Statistical sample selection

The population of the desired number of elements has at least one characteristic trait [1]. Survey of all listed companies in Tehran Stock Exchange is the beginning of 1385 until March of 1390 the stock has been activated. Sampling in this study is a systematic knockout (screening), respectively. Following conditions (characteristic) to determine the sample is considered: Company before the end of 1385 is stock in 1391; its stock has been traded. Significant increase compared to fiscal period to the end of March each year. Company during the years 1385 to 1391 fiscal years has not changed. Some of the listed companies, including banks and financial institutions (investment companies, financial intermediaries, holding and leasing companies) that financial disclosure and corporate governance structures are different, are not

included in the sample. Financial and management information they need (especially in the explanatory notes accompanying the financial statements) is available. Company realized profit in the years 1385 till 1391 is specified. Given the above conditions, a sample size of 58 companies and the number of observations 910 years - the time period 1385 to 1391 are selected as the sample.

7- Materials and Methods

This study because the data are based on the actual financial statements of companies listed on the stock exchange takes place, the quasi-experimental research in the field of positive accounting research the results of the view that tries to identify factors affecting corporate governance and the identification of these factors can help to improve the tax system and can be used for users of financial reports is practical. Moreover, this study is descriptive - correlative in which the data can be used to describe and analyze the relationships between variables. One of the subgroups descriptive research, correlational research, and this correlation and regression due to the nature of the data is after the event.

After collecting the required information from the financial statements, notes and attachments for various applications, the data are concentrated in the Excel database and information required variables have been achieved. Next, enter the data and software Fiaos research hypotheses using correlation and regression equations, through panel data techniques have been tested. In this research, quantitative methods of statistical analysis such as multiple regression analysis were used to painting techniques.

Variables are defined and measured : According to the research hypotheses using regression models are analyzed, are presented in three groups of variables, including the dependent variables, independent and control

Dependent variable: Uncertain tax gap between taxes expression and enterprises have been considered as the dependent variable. The tax gap assessment criteria used in this study is the difference between taxes and uncertain tax paid expressed.

Independent variables:

A) Institutional Investors

In this study, the independent variable is considered as institutional investors and institutions who are dealing with a high volume of securities. In accordance with existing literature, banks, insurance companies, fund retirement, investment companies and other capital markets, they "big boy" also called, among institutional investors with voting rights in decisions and board structure and can influence the company's management can monitor performance [9].

B) Non-duty member of the Board of Directors

Refers to a board member who is not an official administrative liability company and the company does not receive a fixed salary or monthly or yearly. From the perspective of agency theory, managers are not obliged to monitor, and the other board members are responsible for their salaries will be paid on an hourly basis at the meetings [4].

C) Combining the CEO

If the CEO, President or Vice-Chairman is also the situation, CEO duality refers to the task [4]. In this study, the absence of the Chairman or Vice Chairman of the Board and CEO (concentration of power and lack of concentration) extracted from the company's board of directors and the company

reports that the two organizational, it was occupied by a person, an amount that would otherwise be zero.

Control variables: In this study, the three control variables include financial leverage, effective tax rates and firm size has been applied in similar research.

Company size : In order to calculate the market value of the natural logarithm of company size or sales or total assets are used [9]. In the study of the natural logarithm of total assets (Ln assets) is used as the size of the company.

Financial Leverage : Financial leverage is obtained by dividing the debts of the company's assets (Lee and Zavuha 2010). Financial leverage as a control variable in this study is considered.

Effective rate of tax: The effective tax rate divided by the company's uncertain tax profits to be gained in the study as a control variable is considered.

Research model :The model used in this study is as follows.

$$\text{Model (1): Gap} = \alpha_i + \alpha_1 \text{Ins}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{SIZE}_{it} + \alpha_3 \text{LEV}_{it} + \alpha_4 \text{ETR}_{it} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

A significant percentage of institutional ownership coefficient (α_1) means that the model is a significant relationship. Babajani and Abdi research model (1389) have also been used.

$$\text{Model (2): Gap} = \alpha_i + \alpha_1 \text{Out}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{SIZE}_{it} + \alpha_3 \text{LEV}_{it} + \alpha_4 \text{ETR}_{it} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Coefficient of non-bound administrators (α_1) means that the model is a significant relationship. Babajani and Abdi research model (1389) has also been used.

$$\text{Model (3): Gap} = \alpha_i + \alpha_1 \text{CEO}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{SIZE}_{it} + \alpha_3 \text{LEV}_{it} + \alpha_4 \text{ETR}_{it} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Combining the CEO of a significant coefficient (α_1) means that the model is a significant relationship. Babajani and Abdi research model (1389) have also been used.

The variables in the equation are:

Gap: The gap between Tax expression and definitive;

α_i : Constant factor;

α_1 to α_4 : Coefficient in the model;

(Ins): Institutional Investors;

(Out): the percentage of non-responsible managers;

(CEO): combined role of CEO;

(Size): Size Enterprises;

(LEV): financial leverage;

(ETR): The effective rate of tax;

ε : Coefficient of error.

8- Analysis of hypotheses

Overall, the descriptive statistics indicate that the sample has a lot of diversity. For example, descriptive statistics related to the size of each part shows the maximum and minimum value of company assets and

59.337 respectively 90.526.508 and its standard deviation is equal to 8.641.112 which shows the variation of the selected companies and therefore the ability to generalize the results to the research community is exemplary.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of variables

Title	Ins	ETR	SIZE	LEV	TAX	Gap
Average	76.007	0.731	1934332	0.67	12:17	9.235038
Median	78.105	1	400,405	0.65	12:17	0.12811
Maximum	99	1	90526508	3.34	8.18	649.12
At least	9.82	0	59337	12:09	1 -	0.16186-
Standard deviation	17.554	0.4442	8641112	12:34	12:49	53.89594
Number	290	290	290	290	290	290

Analysis of the first hypothesis

First hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between the percentage ownership of institutional shareholders and the percentage difference between the corporate tax and definite expression.

Control variables: In this study, the three control variables include financial leverage, effective tax rates and firm size has been applied in similar research.

Company size :In order to calculate the market value of the natural logarithm of company size or sales or total assets are used [9]. In the study of the natural logarithm of total assets (Ln assets) is used as the size of the company.

Financial Leverage : Financial leverage is obtained by dividing the assets and liabilities of the company (Li & Zhaohua 2010). Financial leverage as a control variable in this study is considered.

Effective rate of tax : The effective tax rate divided by the company's uncertain tax profits to be gained in the study as a control variable is considered.

Research model : The model used in this study is as follows.

$$\text{Model (1): } \text{Gap} = \alpha_i + \alpha_1 \text{Ins}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{SIZE}_{it} + \alpha_3 \text{LEV}_{it} + \alpha_4 \text{ETR}_{it} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

A significant percentage of institutional ownership coefficient (α_1) means that the model is a significant relationship. Babajani and Abdi research model (1389) have also been used.

$$\text{Model (2): Gap} = \alpha_i + \alpha_1 \text{Out}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{SIZE}_{it} + \alpha_3 \text{LEV}_{it} + \alpha_4 \text{ETR}_{it} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

A significant percentage of institutional ownership coefficient (α_1) means that the model is a significant relationship. Babajani and Abdi research model (1389) have also been used.

$$\text{Model (3): Gap} = \alpha_i + \alpha_1 \text{CEO}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{SIZE}_{it} + \alpha_3 \text{LEV}_{it} + \alpha_4 \text{ETR}_{it} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Combining the CEO of a significant coefficient (α_1) means that the model is a significant relationship. Babajani and Abdi research model (1389) have also been used.

The variables in the equation are:

Gap: Gap between Tax expression and definitive;

α_i : Constant factor;

α_1 to α_4 : Coefficient in the model

(Ins): Institutional Investors;

(Out): The percentage of non-responsible managers;

(CEO): Combining the CEO

(LEV): financial leverage;

(ETR): The effective rate of tax;

ε : Coefficient of error

Analysis of hypotheses : Overall, the descriptive statistics indicate that the sample has a lot of diversity. For example, descriptive statistics related to the size of each part shows the maximum and minimum value of company assets and 59.337 respectively 90.526.508 and standard deviation equal to 8.641.112 which is also indicated by the variety of choice, and so is the ability to generalize sample results to the research community.

Analysis of the first hypothesis : First hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between the percentage ownership of institutional shareholders and the percentage difference between the corporate tax and definite expression. The hypothesis of the study of the relationship between institutional shareholders and percentage of ownership between corporate taxes and definite expression (expression and uncertain tax gap between taxes on corporations) proposed using Model 1 was tested and the results Chow test (fixed effects cross-sectional time constant results) and the results of the above analysis and assumptions are described in the tables below have been calculated.

$$\text{Model (1): Gap} = \alpha_i + \alpha_1 \text{Ins}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{SIZE}_{it} + \alpha_3 \text{LEV}_{it} + \alpha_4 \text{ETR}_{it} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Combining the data of the first test, F (Chow test) in order to choose between two alternative ways of Pooling and Panel model estimation is performed. In this study, depending on the model, fixed effects are cross-sectional and time-tested. Table 2 and Table 3 show the results of the regression F test to determine appropriateness in relation to the hypothesis. The combination of cross-sectional data is examined as well as their simultaneous effects. The fixed effects model is for each of the years when an intercept and the fixed effects model, an intercept point for each of these companies is presented. It's time to see the intercept are statistically significantly different from each other or not, we used the Chow test. So the hypotheses H0 and H1 are expressed as follows:

H0: All intercept equal $\leftrightarrow$ Pooled

H1: the intercept are different $\leftrightarrow$ fixed effects model when either cross or both.

Therefore, the constant model (intercept) in each of these modes is as follows:

- 1- Pooled α_0
- 2- panel type fixed effects time
- 3- Panel type fixed effects time
- 4- Panel type and time period fixed effects

According to the Chow test statistical probability model is smaller than 5%, the hypothesis was rejected based on the equality of the intercept and the fixed effects model is preferred.

Table 2: Results of cross-sectional fixed effects

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests			
Test cross-section fixed effects			
Effects Test	Statistic	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	7.2016	(57228)	0
Cross-section Chi-square	293.8954	57	0

Table 3: Results of fixed effects time

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests			
Test period fixed effects			
Effects Test	Statistic	df	Prob.
Period F	0.305283	(4.281)	0.8743
Period Chi-square	1.2575	4	0.8685

Given the Chow test statistic for fixed effects in cross probability smaller than 5% and the fixed effects time the probability is greater than 5%. Thus, hypothesis H1 is based on the equality of the intercept for fixed effects reject the cross-sectional and fixed effects model is preferred. Results related to hypothesis testing in Table 4 are presented.

Table 4: Analysis of hypothesis

Estimated period: 1385-1391	
Gap = $\alpha_i + \alpha_1 Ins_{it} + \alpha_2 SIZE_{it} + \alpha_3 LEV_{it} + \alpha_4 ETR_{it} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$	
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)	
Adjusted coefficient of determination	0.816953

F-statistic	16.68165				
Standard deviation of the regression	20.7468				
Probability (Prob)	0				
Camera test - Watson	2.057921				
Explanatory variable	Confidence level	Probability	T-statistics	Standard error	Coefficient
(Institutional investors) Ins	Meaningless	0.1464	1.45717	0.048706	0.070972
(Size) SIZE	Meaningless	0.8452	0.19547-	0.000000229	0.0000000448-
(Effective tax rate) ETR	99%	0	56.94568	0.171649	9.774669
(Financial leverage) LEV	99%	0.0092	2.62772-	3.301023	8.67415-
(Intercept) C	95%	0.0428	2.037237	3.983328	8.114982

According to the F statistic and its associated probability can be concluded that the significant regression equation is confidence level of 99%. The results of the test camera - Watson (lack of autocorrelation error terms) is to model the relative independence of the data. The model is adjusted coefficient of determination represents the degree of independent variables to the dependent variable (the tax gap). According to Table 4 is the coefficient of determination adjusted for the 81% model. Thus, on average, 81% of variability is explained by this model. Due to the possibility of changing the percentage ownership of institutional shareholders is greater than 5%. Therefore, this variable is not significant at the 95% confidence level in the model. Therefore there is no significant relationship between the percentage ownership of institutional shareholders and the percentage difference between expression and certain corporate tax (the tax gap). Considering the potential covariates, variable size with probability greater than 5% and the effective rate of taxation of financial leverage variables, the probability is less than 1%. The auxiliary variable firm size is not significant at the 95% confidence level in the model, but such leverage, effective tax rates in the model were significant at the 99% confidence level. Due to the lack of significant change in the percentage ownership of institutional shareholders and thus does not model the relationship between the percentage ownership of institutional shareholders and the percentage difference between expression and certain tax-companies (Cleft tax) is research hypothesis.

Analysis of the second hypothesis : Second hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between the percentage of non-executive Directors and the percentage difference between the duty and the definitive expression of corporate taxes. This hypothesis concerning the relationship between the variables of directors of non-duty board and discordance Tax expression and certain companies (the gap between taxes expression and uncertain tax companies) raised 1 and model 2 was tested and the results of these tests Chow (fixed effects cross-sectional time constant results) and the results of the above analysis and assumptions are described in the tables below have been calculated. This hypothesis concerning the relationship between the variables of the non-bound executives and board of expression and certain corporate tax differences (gaps between expression and uncertain tax corporate tax) is introduced and tested using model 2 and the results

Chow test (sectional fixed effects, time constant results) and the results of the analysis of the above hypothesis, the following tables are calculated and described.

$$\text{Gap} = \alpha_i + \alpha_1 \text{Out}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{SIZE}_{it} + \alpha_3 \text{LEV}_{it} + \alpha_4 \text{ETR}_{it} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Chow test results in Tables 4-5 and 4-6 are presented.

According to the F statistic and its associated probability can be concluded that the significant regression equation is confidence level of 99%. The results of the test camera - Watson (lack of autocorrelation error terms) is to model the relative independence of the data. The coefficient of determination adjusted model, expression levels of the independent variables is on the dependent variable (the tax gap). According to Table (4.10) the coefficient of determination adjusted model is 73%. Thus, on average, 73% of the variability is explained by this model. Due to the possibility of changing the composition of the Managing Director is larger than 5%. Therefore, this variable is not significant at the 95% confidence level in the model. Therefore, the combined role of CEO and discordance between expression and certain corporate tax (the tax gap) a significant relationship exists with regard to the possibility of auxiliary variables, variables with a probability greater than 5% and variables of firm size and financial leverage effective tax rate of the probability is less than 1%. The auxiliary variable firm size is not significant at the 95% confidence level, but the model parameters and variables leverage, effective tax rate variable in the model were significant at the 99% confidence level. Due to the lack of significant combined role model and therefore no relationship between the CEO and the CEO of the combined role of taxes between expression and disruption of the company the third hypothesis: is rejected.

Limitations of the study : Some of the inherent limitations of the study and some of the conditions and limitations are in our study. The main limitations of this study exist in the interpretation and generalizability of the results should be considered to be a chorus of: According to the study, and we need to collect a lot of variables, each of them should have the various sources referred, therefore, we collected data on the dependent variable, and we needed to uncertain tax companies studied. Because of taxes by tax officers in some cases there is a large difference therefore, the detection of taxes by the tax authorities in the legal deadlines and make sure it is not a long process and collect certain taxes.

Results

In this study, the relationship between some important measure of corporate governance, the percentage difference between the tax and the final expression is evaluated. Since the company is considered as one of the beneficiaries; if standards of corporate governance principles that acknowledge the rights of all stakeholders in the company are expected to be present tax and tax and tax and tax expression and definitive diagnosis is largely consistent, In which case the share of corporate profits are determined to be more precise. In this study, the four most important criteria for corporate governance, including institutional shareholders ownership percentage, the percentage of non-duty members in the composition of the board and the CEO (duality duties CEO) of the company, such as the control the three variables of the company, The effective rate of tax and financial leverage is used as the dependent variable in the final expression and the tax gap is considered. Survey of all listed companies in Tehran Stock Exchange are in stock at the beginning of 1385 until March of 1390 and have been active in the sampling of this research system playoff (screening) fifty-eight of this company is have been selected . It uses the extracted data from various sources and databases, especially databases and CD Stock Exchange, the company's financial statements, the application has been made to devise a new processor and outcomes. For the analysis, data mining, and hypothesis testing research results of correlation and regression equations from panel data methods and software Excel and 6Eviews is used and the following results were obtained. In this section, in order to analyze the data, three main hypotheses designed to examine the results are discussed as follows.

First hypothesis test results : The first hypothesis about the relationship between the percentage ownership of institutional shareholders and the percentage difference between the corporate tax and definite expression

has been proposed and tested. The results indicate there is no significant direct relationship between these two variables. This means that institutional shareholders, the tax gap by increasing or decreasing expression and definitively do not play any role. Among the control variables of the study, the effective tax rate varies significantly with 99% probability and its relation to the tax gap, is directly financial leverage and significant variable associated with a 99% probability that the tax gap, reverse and variable size, is meaningless; it has no connection with the tax gap. The results of this hypothesis are consistent with results of Babajani and Abdi (1389).

Second hypothesis test results : The second hypothesis about the relationship between the percentage of non-responsible managers and the board of directors of the companies discussed and examined differences in taxes and definite expression has been addressed. The results indicate there is no significant direct relationship between these two variables. That is not the duty of the Board of Directors had no role in increasing or decreasing the expression of certain tax gap. Among the control variables of the study, the effective tax rate varies significantly with 99% probability and its relation to the tax gap, is directly financial leverage and significant variable associated with a 99% probability that the tax gap, reverse and variable size, non-sense is not so with regard to the tax gap. The results of this hypothesis results Babajani and Abdi (1389) are consistent.

Third hypothesis test results: The third hypothesis concerning the combined roles of CEO and discordance between expression and certain corporate tax has been proposed and tested. The results indicate there is no significant direct relationship between these two variables. This means that the separation of CEO and Chairman (or Vice Chairman) of the Board had no role in increasing or decreasing the expression of certain tax gap. Among the control variables of the study, the effective tax rate varies significantly with 99% probability and its relation to the tax gap, and direct financial leverage variable with a significant 99% probability and its relation to the tax gap reverse and the size of the company, is pointless, so no connection with the tax gap. The results of this hypothesis results Babajani and Abdi (1389) are consistent.

Recommendations : With regard to the issue of tax transparency and corporate governance issues that have been investigated in recent years the frequency has a significant role in the development of enterprises, thus, the importance of these issues and conduct research in this field is necessary to achieve corporate goals. So if more and more detailed investigations are carried out in this area during the coming years will lead to a lower probability of error and the ability to use its results has to increase. Initially proposed to achieve better results from this research will be presented and examined it, and then conducted suggestions for future research are discussed.

Recommendations based on research findings: Given that this is a reasonable expectation, if institutional shareholders have good performance gap between expression and certain corporate taxes were reduced as expected, but the existing theoretical concepts, corporate governance mechanisms and financing gap between expression and taxes there was a definite relationship. This indicates the lack of the proper role of corporate governance mechanisms, so it is recommended to institutional investors and other stakeholders in terms of their rights to play their role more appropriate for those efforts.

Suggestions for future research

As the results indicate no significant difference between means of expression and certain tax dispute appears to have been one of the main reasons for the lack of clear information on the economic activities of individuals in society. So transparent - information and reducing corporate taxes and definite expression research recommendations for future research are as follows:

- 1- The present study can be done about a particular industry; the research has been done in all industries.
- 2- The future of research data for longer periods to increase the validity and reliability of models.
- 3- The relationship between other measures of corporate governance uncertain tax gap Tax expression and companies.
- 4- Relationship between Corporate Governance and tax transparency.
- 5- Relationship between Corporate Governance and Earnings Management.
- 6- Relationship between Corporate Governance and tax evasion.

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